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PROLEPSIS

Horizon Europe-funded project developing a novel personalised digital care ecosystem for people with PsA

iPROLEPSIS project newsletter | Issue No. 9

July 2025

Welcome to the 9th edition of the iPROLEPSIS project newsletter! In this issue, we bring you insights into European advances in digital rheumatology, iPROLEPSIS-PDPID Study, and key events.

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Call for IEEE HealthCom 2025 Workshop Papers

Peer-reviewed publication in the **Lancet**

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Research News

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the European Union

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Project Highlights

Call for IEEE HealthCom 2025 Workshop Papers – *deadline extended*

The **iPROLEPSIS** and **AI-PROGNOSIS** projects are co-organising a workshop titled: “**AI-enabled Digital Health Tools for Non-Communicable Diseases: From Concepts to Impact**” as part of the **IEEE HealthCom 2025** conference, taking place on 21–23 October 2025 in Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates.

Authors are invited to submit original research, position papers, or case studies with practical highlights. Topics of interest include (but are not limited to):

- Predictive models for early detection, risk assessment, and prognosis of NCDs
- Digital biomarkers and wearable sensors for NCDs
- Machine learning for personalized treatment, disease management, and precision medicine
- AI in remote care, mHealth, and telemedicine for NCDs
- Regulatory and ethical considerations in AI-enabled software as medical device
- Data quality, fairness, and explainability in AI health applications
- User-centered design in AI-enabled health technology for chronic conditions
- Translational pathways from research prototypes to scalable digital health solutions

Important dates:

NEW

Workshop paper submission **July 15, 2025**
Acceptance notifications **August 15, 2025**
Camera Ready papers **August 30, 2025**

[More information here](#)

For any questions, please contact:

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IEEE International Conference on E-health
Networking, Application & Services

More info healthcom2025.ieee-healthcom.org

Call for workshop papers

AI-enabled Digital Health Tools for Non-Communicable Diseases: From Concepts to Impact

21-23 October 2025
Abu Dhabi
United Arab Emirates

Paper submission deadline extended to July 15, 2025

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Project Highlights

European advances in digital rheumatology: explainable insights and personalized digital health tools for psoriatic arthritis

Hadjileontiadis L.J., Charisis V., Hadjidimitriou S., Dias S.B., Apostolidis G., Dimaridis G., et al. (2025). *The Lancet eClinicalMedicine*.

A recent **peer-reviewed publication** in the **Lancet eClinicalMedicine** presents the iPROLEPSIS initiative as a comprehensive European effort to advance psoriatic arthritis (PsA) care through digital innovation and personalised, patient-centred approaches.

The paper details how the project addresses **current gaps in PsA diagnosis and management by integrating real-world data, wearable sensors, and explainable AI models.**

[*Read the full paper*](#)

iPROLEPSIS Featured in Khalifa University Research News

Khalifa University Research News recently spotlighted iPROLEPSIS and our mission to transform psoriatic arthritis care through digital innovation.

[*Read the full article*](#)

The article highlights how iPROLEPSIS is advancing early detection, personalised treatment, and patient-centered digital tools through explainable AI and real-world data.

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Project Highlights

iPROLEPSIS-PDPID Study: Ongoing Patient Recruitment

The PsA Digital Phenotyping and Inflammation Drivers (iPROLEPSIS-PDPID) study continues active recruitment across the Netherlands, the UK, Portugal, and Greece.

the Netherlands

the UK

Portugal

Greece

217

*participants have
been recruited*

As of June 2025, 217 participants have been enrolled – up from 152 in April – with steady growth at all sites as engagement increases.

Using smart devices and clinical data, the study supports the development of AI-driven tools for personalised monitoring and flare prediction in psoriatic arthritis (PsA).

Participants contribute daily data via the iPROLEPSIS app and Garmin smartwatches, helping to inform the development of digital biomarkers for PsA care.

*Garmin Vivoactive
5 smartwatch*

*heart rate, sleep quality,
and physical activity*

Events

▶▶▶ iPROLEPSIS Games Presented at HiTech Program Final Pitch

26 June 2025
Lisbon, Portugal

On June 26, 2025, the **iPROLEPSIS Games** were showcased during the final pitch session of the **HiTech Program** at the Thalia Theater in Lisbon, Portugal.

Representing FMH/IST-ULisboa, Samuel Gomes, Bárbara Ramalho, and Filipa Magalhães introduced the iPROLEPSIS Games to an audience of investors and stakeholders interested in innovative health solutions.

▶▶▶ EIT Health Morning Health Talk

2 June 2025
Athens, Greece

On June 2, 2025, the iPROLEPSIS project was presented at the **1st Morning Health Talk – Greece**, part of the **EIT Health Morning Health Talks** series. The event, titled “Co-Creating Health Innovation Ecosystems: Empowering Providers and Citizens Beyond Financial Incentives”, was organised by EIT Health Greece and hosted at the National Documentation Centre in Athens.

Dr. Vasileios Charisis from Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH) presented an overview of iPROLEPSIS, developing a novel personalised digital care ecosystem for people with Psoriatic arthritis (PsA).

Events

The session brought together a diverse group of participants from across the health innovation landscape, including:

- EIT and EIT Health Greece representatives
- European Digital Innovation Hubs – Health Hub
- European Network of Living Labs
- Digital health consultants from the Greek Ministry of Digital Governance
- Public and private hospitals
- Private health insurance companies, homecare providers, and telemedicine companies

The event offered valuable opportunities for sharing perspectives, building connections, and exploring collaborative strategies for the future of healthcare innovation.

➤➤➤ iPROLEPSIS presented at the COMFORT-EU Plenary Meeting

15-16 May 2025
Thessaloniki, Greece

Dr. Vasileios Charisis (Aristotle University of Thessaloniki) took part in the **2nd Plenary Meeting of the COMFORT-EU project** (15–16 May 2025), where he presented the iPROLEPSIS project and introduced our work on a Trustworthy AI framework for healthcare.

Meetings like this offer a valuable opportunity to connect with other research teams, share knowledge, and explore ways to collaborate. In the fast-evolving field of AI in healthcare, collaboration is essential – helping us learn from each other and develop better, safer solutions for real-world use.

Events

Plenary meeting

13-14 May 2025
Oxford, UK

The iPROLEPSIS consortium came together on 13–14 May 2025 for its 6th Plenary Meeting, hosted by the University of Oxford in Oxford, UK.

The two-day meeting covered updates on various parts of the project, including system development, clinical studies, data harmonisation, and user needs. It was a great opportunity for partners to share progress, discuss challenges, and align on next steps. Workshops helped address open issues and refine priorities for the coming months. On the first day, the consortium also welcomed feedback from the External Advisory Board, offering helpful guidance on recent developments.

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Upcoming Events

GRAPPA Annual Meeting 2025

10-12 July 2025
Bogota, Colombia

iPROLEPSIS project will be presented during the Soapbox Session at the GRAPPA Annual Meeting 2025. The presentation will provide an overview of the **project's key objectives, clinical studies, and emerging results** – highlighting how iPROLEPSIS is advancing innovation in psoriatic disease research and care.

[Learn more](#)

IEEE HealthCom 2025

21-23 October 2025
Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates

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[Learn more](#)

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